

On the use of physics-based constraints and validation KPI for data-driven elastoplastic constitutive modelling

Rúben Lourenço^{a,b,c} ,
A. Andrade-Campos^{a,b,c}

^a Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^b TEMA - Centre for Mechanical Technology and Automation, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^c LASI - Intelligent Systems Associate Laboratory, Campus Azurém, 4800-058 Guimarães, Portugal

^d Department of Civil Engineering, Bursa Uludağ University, Gorukle Campus, Bursa Bursa, Türkiye

^e Dept. of Electronics, Telecommunications and Informatics, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^f IT - Institute of Telecommunications, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

^g IEETA - Institute of Electronics and Informatics Engineering of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal

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ABSTRACT

Constitutive modelling based on machine learning (ML) approaches has surged in the last couple of decades due to novel and more robust model architectures and computational power. The dependency of these models on large amounts of training data can be mitigated by imposing some phenomenological knowledge as constraints, which also helps maintain the quality of learning. This paper highlights the importance of physics-based constraints in elastoplastic data-driven constitutive modelling and focuses on model validation methods. Specifically, seven constraints applied to elastoplastic behaviour are identified that can be used during the model training process. To study the effects of these constraints, a set of recurrent neural network (RNN) models is trained using data from virtual mechanical experiments, based on a biaxial cruciform specimen. The models' ability to accurately learn and predict the fundamental constitutive behaviour is then assessed using the different validation checkpoints, which include (i) statistical metrics, (ii) tests on previously unseen data, from virtual experiments based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, (iii) external key performance indicators (KPI) and (iv) single-element finite element analysis (FEA) tests. It was observed that the benefits of adding constraints to the training process were three-fold, resulting in (i) improved model predictive capacity, as well as (ii) enhanced extrapolation capabilities when tested on different mechanical specimens and (iii) overall improved training speed and stability. The use of independent validation KPI for data-driven constitutive modelling is highlighted and suggested as standard practice in future researches in the field.

1. Introduction

The complex behaviour of metals is related to a combination of their microstructural characteristics and the mechanisms governing their deformation and failure [1,2]. Along the years, many constitutive laws have been proposed to model these behaviours. Conventional constitutive models are developed based on first-order principles and theoretical principles derived from

* Corresponding author at: Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, 3810-193 Aveiro, Portugal.
E-mail address: rubenl@ua.pt (R. Lourenço).

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empirical observations, involving many assumptions. As a result, a set of laws is translated into mathematical expressions relying on a variety of empirical parameters, which need be calibrated. Parameter calibration ensures the compatibility between the experimental and the numerically simulated response [3,4]. As model complexity grows, the number of parameters increases requiring extensive experimental campaigns, which are expensive and time-consuming [5]. The phenomenological nature of such models means the adjacent explicit form is generally biased, due to the simplifying assumptions of first-order principles [6]. Moreover, a given model is not guaranteed to provide good results in different settings from those used to calibrate it [7].

Artificial neural networks (ANNs) have the potential to lead a paradigm shift in the field of constitutive modelling [8]. A key advantage is that ANNs do not require any assumptions about the explicit form of the model, effectively eliminating the need to identify unknown constitutive parameters [9]. As such, ANNs are able to learn patterns implicitly purely from data allowing to mitigate the biases inherent to conventional constitutive models, given sufficient data and model capacity [6]. The first attempt to explore the use of ANNs for implicit constitutive modelling is attributed to Ghaboussi et al. (1991) [10]. The authors trained a feedforward neural network (FFNN) to capture the biaxial and cyclic behaviour of concrete, reporting promising results. A pioneering application to metal behaviour was led by Furukawa and Yagawa (1998) [11], who extended the concept to viscoplasticity. The authors tested the model with experimental data and found it to be highly accurate with negligible errors. Hashash et al. (2004) [12] contributed with the development of an explicit formulation for the consistent material stiffness matrix for ANN-based constitutive models.

Modelling path-dependent plasticity using ANNs is challenging due to the history dependency effect. Simple feedforward architectures are unable to capture the phenomenon, as there is no mechanism that relates the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [13,14]. In earlier works, the process involved feeding stress and strain tensors from previous time steps, along with additional internal variables of the model, as input features into a FFNN to predict the material response [11,15,16]. The approach resulted in added network complexity and the use of internal variables meant that some sort of assumption had to be made about the explicit form of the constitutive law. Moreover, internal variables often lack direct physical meaning, exist primarily in a numerical sense, and are generally not accessible through standard experiments. However, exceptions exist in specific modelling frameworks, such as crystal plasticity [17], where certain internal variables like dislocation densities have clear physical interpretations. Further advancements in computational resources, allowed for the development of more sophisticated network architectures, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). Contrary to FFNNs, RNNs are particularly robust for implicit constitutive modelling due to built-in memory cells that capture the effects of path-dependent behaviour [18]. Using sequences of strain tensors that spanning from a number of time stages in the past up to the current time stage t , a RNN can capture the temporal dependencies, allowing it to predict the corresponding stress state accurately. Such capabilities have resulted in a variety of works reported in the field [13,14,19–24].

In general, ANN-based models require a large amount of training data in order to obtain accurate predictions. In the context of material modelling, it often involves generating large synthetic or experimental datasets. Nonetheless, a well-trained ANN is still a black-box model, which is not easily interpretable and may originate spurious non-physical responses. The issue is addressed encoding physics-based information, either by modifying the original architecture or adding extra residual terms to the loss function. The approach allows to improve both interpolation and extrapolation accuracy, helps to avoid overfitting and allows for faster training [25]. Within this context, Raissi et al. (2019) [26] firstly introduced physics-informed neural networks (PINNs), allowing the model to respect symmetries, invariances and conservation laws governing the observed data. In more recent work, Borkowski et al. (2022) [27] used regularization techniques to maintain a non-negative plastic power density throughout the loading history to maintain thermodynamic consistency. Similarly, Weber et al. (2023) [28] used constrained neural network models for elastoplasticity by incorporating material stationarity, stability, symmetry and normalization in an optimization algorithm. The results have shown improved predictive accuracy, convergence and stability. Thermodynamic principles have also been incorporated as physics-based knowledge into model architectures during training to enhance accuracy [29–32]. A wide variety of studies applied to hyperelastic materials have also been presented with a strong focus on the subject. Linka et al. (2021) [33] developed an ANN model to capture the behaviour of hyperelastic materials, which were then implemented in finite element analysis (FEA) solver. The authors were able to train the model in a low-data regime through the incorporation of material knowledge from continuum mechanics into the training process. Recent studies employed an unsupervised model discovery framework called EUCLID for hyperelastic materials [34–36]. Here, physics-based constraints are implemented in the loss function as regularization penalty to train the model without access to stress labels. Weber et al. (2021) [37] demonstrated that introducing constraints based on energy conservation, normalization and material symmetries for hyperelastic materials leads to improved learning behaviour, particularly when dealing with noisy data or smaller datasets. Kalina et al. (2022) [38] also introduced an ANN-based approach for the automated modelling of hyperelastic materials. The authors trained the ANN using plane stress synthetic data and applied a thermodynamically consistent correction to the model weights to obtain highly accurate results for the simulation of three-dimensional samples. Similarly, As'ad et al. (2022) [39] proposed a methodology to train mechanics-informed ANNs by adding physical constraints like consistency, objectivity and stability conditions to the loss function. According to the authors, the additions enhanced the model robustness outside the training domain and reduced the sensitivity to noise. Tac et al. (2022a) [40] replaced explicit hyperelastic models with ANNs to predict the strain energy and its derivatives with respect to strain invariants. The authors also designed a loss function to enforce polyconvexity of the strain energy as a constraint to ensure material stability in FEA simulations. Additional studies in the same field also include those of Liu et al. (2020) [41]; Klein et al. (2022) [42] and Tac et al. (2022b) [43]. This slew of works shows the popularity of hyperelastic materials for ANN-based constitutive modelling. The related papers are also heavily focused on model constraints. Hyperelastic families of models are particularly suitable for ANN modelling due to their energy-based formulations. This allows for the effective application of physics-based constraints and for the straightforward calculation of stress via automatic

differentiation. In contrast, path-dependent elastoplastic material formulations involve yield criteria, plastic flow rules and hardening laws, which are more complex to encode into an ANN framework. To address these challenges, this paper aims to identify various physics-based relationships that can potentially be used as constraints when training an ANN-based elastoplastic constitutive model.

Model validation is a crucial step in the data-driven modelling workflow. Besides providing an unbiased evaluation of the model's performance, ensuring it can handle new inputs effectively, it also serves as a benchmark to compare different modelling approaches. In the context of data-driven constitutive modelling, where it is imperative to guarantee physically consistent solutions, the importance of the validation step is even more relevant. Here, the standard error metrics alone are insufficient to discern between models and may hide certain effects. According to Fuhg et al. (2024) [44], it is crucial to adopt validation tests using different experiments that encompass loading paths not included in the original dataset. It is also important to adopt additional metrics, as a complement to the standard error statistics, that provide a more in-depth assessment of the model's performance. As such, this paper also explores four different validation approaches to evaluate developed data-driven constitutive models. First, model performance is evaluated based on the usual statistical metrics using the validation dataset, under different loading conditions. Second, the predictive accuracy is evaluated on additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, different from those used for training. Additionally, external key performance indicators (KPI) are used to further assess the accuracy of the data-driven constitutive models. Finally, various single-element tests are conducted to evaluate the integration of the developed models into a FEA solver.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2, introduces the theoretical background related to general elastoplastic behaviour and provides an overview of the requirements for constitutive equations that can potentially be used as constraints for model training. In Section 3, RNNs with gated recurrent units (GRUs) are introduced along with the corresponding mathematical background. The chosen RNN architectures, as well as the data generation and training procedures, are detailed in Section 4. In Section 5, the importance of validation within the general data-driven modelling workflow is highlighted and new validation checks aimed at data-driven constitutive modelling, in particular, are also proposed and described in detail. Finally, in Section 6, results showing the effects of the addition of physics-based constraint for model training are presented. The trained RNN-based models' performance is evaluated based on the previously proposed validation methodology.

2. Material modelling

2.1. Elastoplasticity

A material under load undergoes plastic deformation starting at the uniaxial yield stress σ_0 , beyond which hardening phenomena take place. Reversing the load at a given strain ϵ , plastic deformation ceases to increase and stress starts to linearly decrease with strain, with a gradient equal to the Young's modulus, E [2]. Once the stress reaches zero, the strain remaining in the material is the plastic strain ϵ^P , whereas the recovered strain ϵ^e is the elastic strain, such that [2]:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^e + \epsilon^P. \quad (1)$$

The constitutive relation maps the elastic strain to the stress through the tangent stiffness tensor \mathbf{C} as [1]:

$$\sigma = \mathbf{C}\epsilon^e. \quad (2)$$

There are plenty of developed yield criteria, with the most commonly used in engineering practice being that of von Mises. The criterion relies on the knowledge of an equivalent stress σ_{VM} , the von Mises stress, defined in tensor notation as [2]:

$$\sigma_{\text{VM}} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{2} (\sigma' : \sigma')}, \quad (3)$$

where σ' is the deviatoric stress tensor. Similarly, an effective plastic strain rate \dot{p} can be established, such that:

$$\dot{p} = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} (\dot{\epsilon}^P : \dot{\epsilon}^P)}. \quad (4)$$

The yield function, thus, assumes the following representation [2]:

$$f(\sigma, p) = \sigma_{\text{VM}}(\sigma) - \sigma_Y(p), \quad (5)$$

which is written as a function of the stress σ and accumulated plastic strain p , such that:

$$p = \int \dot{p} dt. \quad (6)$$

The performance of the material thus depends on the previous states of stress and strain, that is, plasticity is path-dependent [11]. As such, the plastic range can be characterized by multiples internal variables; in the case of isotropic hardening, the drag stress R is introduced, and the yield function is modified as [2]:

$$f = J(\sigma) - R - k \leq 0, \quad (7)$$

where k is a material constant and J is a distance in the stress space. The plastic flow follows the normality condition [45,46]:

$$d\epsilon^P = d\lambda \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma}, \quad (8)$$

which states that the increment in the plastic strain tensor occurs in the direction normal to the tangent to the yield surface at the load point [47]. The plastic multiplier $d\lambda$ is derived from the hardening rule after employing the consistency condition [46] $f = df = 0$. The constitutive relation from Eq. (2) can then be rewritten in the general form [48]:

$$\dot{\sigma} = \mathbf{H}\dot{\epsilon} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{C}\dot{\epsilon} & \text{if } f < 0 \\ \left[\mathbf{C} - \frac{\left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right) \left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)^T}{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)^T \left(\mathbf{C} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \sigma} \right)} \right] \dot{\epsilon} & \text{if } f = 0 \end{cases}, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{H} is a general tangent stiffness tensor that degenerates into the elastic tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} under elasticity. In FEA, the constitutive model is responsible for updating not only the stress according to the current stress–strain state and strain increment, but also the material stiffness, which is obtained iteratively by means of the Newton–Raphson method. This phenomenological approach has been successfully used in FEA software for decades, however, model calibration still poses as an open problem and shows limitations when applied to complex material behaviours, due to its predefined mathematical formulation and lack of flexibility. For more details concerning phenomenological constitutive modelling and their classical equations, the reader is advised to refer to [1,2].

2.2. Requirements for constitutive equations

2.2.1. Laws of thermodynamics

The laws of thermodynamics impose two restrictions on stress–strain relationships. The first law requires that the work done by stress must either be stored as recoverable internal energy in the solid or dissipated as heat [1]. As such, a local entropy generation, or intrinsic dissipation in the material is defined, such that:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon} + \theta \dot{\eta} - \dot{E}, \quad (10)$$

where σ is the stress tensor, $\dot{\epsilon}$ the strain rate tensor, θ the absolute temperature, η the entropy per unit volume and E the internal energy per unit volume. The second law of thermodynamics requires that, if a sample of material is subjected to a cycle of deformation, starting and ending with identical strain and internal energy, the total work must be positive or zero, such that [1,28,49]:

$$\gamma_{\text{loc}} \geq 0. \quad (11)$$

The thermodynamic consistency for a constitutive model is ensured through the Clausius-Duhem inequality, defined in an isothermal and small strain regime as [50]:

$$D = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon} - \rho \dot{\Phi} \geq 0, \quad (12)$$

where D is the mechanical dissipation, Φ the free-energy which depends on the internal variables and ρ the material density. Given that the constitutive model does not provide access to the free-energy, a weaker form is preferred here and could be defined as [49,50]:

$$D^0 = \oint \sigma : d\epsilon \geq 0. \quad (13)$$

Considering that the stress update is based on the increment of total strain from ϵ^n to ϵ^{n+1} , a closed path could be constructed such that a second step is performed back to ϵ^n (see Fig. 1), that is:

$$D^0 = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma^n + \sigma^{n+1}) \Delta\epsilon_1 + \frac{1}{2} (\sigma^{n+1} + \sigma^*) \Delta\epsilon_2 \geq 0. \quad (14)$$

Given that $\Delta\epsilon_1 = \epsilon^{n+1} - \epsilon^n$ and $\Delta\epsilon_2 = -\Delta\epsilon_1$, the above relationship can be simplified to:

$$D^0 = \frac{1}{2} (\sigma^n - \sigma^*) : \Delta\epsilon \geq 0, \quad (15)$$

where σ^* is the stress response after returning to the origin of the path at ϵ^n . Although this inequality is weaker than the one defined in Eq. (11), it can be easily implemented in the context of ANN-based constitutive modelling. Nonetheless, it requires evaluating the model response at an additional fictitious step in the strain space [28,49].

Another requirement that stems from the second law of thermodynamics is that the plastic power must be non-negative to obey the second law of thermodynamics, in the absence of damage and heat conduction, i.e. [27]:

$$\dot{w}^p = \sigma : \dot{\epsilon}^p \geq 0. \quad (16)$$

A negative plastic dissipation would imply a decrease in temperature as a result of inelastic deformation, which would violate the second law of thermodynamics. Hence, plastic dissipation must remain non-negative and non-decreasing as it represents irreversibly lost energy. From here, it naturally follows that the accumulated plastic work

$$w^p = \int_0^t \dot{w}^p dt, \quad (17)$$

should be non-decreasing [27]. However, since plastic work includes both plastic dissipation and plastic free energy, such condition may not always be verified [51]. For example, in the event of reverse loading (e.g., in kinematic hardening models), plastic free energy can be partially recovered, causing the accumulated plastic work to decrease without violating thermodynamic principles. Nevertheless, in the current paper, and for the sake of simplification, plastic free energy was not considered.

Fig. 1. Dissipated energy D^0 , after two consecutive steps $\Delta\epsilon$ and $-\Delta\epsilon$ in the strain space.

2.2.2. Drucker's postulate

The Drucker's postulate states that the work done by the tractions through the displacements is positive or zero [1,28], such that:

$$\Delta\sigma : \Delta\epsilon \geq 0. \tag{18}$$

The condition is not a thermodynamic law and it does not have a physical meaning. Nonetheless, it is required to be fulfilled to ensure the uniqueness of the boundary value problem.

2.2.3. Tangent stiffness symmetry

For a general material in a three-dimensional stress state, the tangent stiffness \mathbf{C} is a symmetric fourth order tensor with 21 independent components. If the material is orthotropic, it gets reduced to nine independent components and the general mapping between the elastic strain and stress may be expressed in matrix form as [2]:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ \sigma_{yy} \\ \sigma_{zz} \\ \tau_{yz} \\ \tau_{xz} \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & & & \\ & C_{22} & C_{23} & & & \\ & & C_{33} & & & \\ & & & C_{44} & & \\ & & & & C_{55} & \\ & & & & & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_{xx} \\ \epsilon_{yy} \\ \epsilon_{zz} \\ 2\epsilon_{yz} \\ 2\epsilon_{xz} \\ 2\epsilon_{xy} \end{Bmatrix}. \tag{19}$$

The major symmetries of \mathbf{C} mean that the physically correct state of stress is the one that maximizes the plastic dissipation for a given plastic strain rate [28]. When the material undergoes plastic deformation, a general tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} may be considered as in Eq. (9), which remains symmetric. Additionally, when strain hardening effects are present, \mathbf{H} is positive definite, to ensure that the strain energy is positive and weakly convex [48,52]. The latter is also a sufficient condition for the uniqueness of the elastoplastic boundary value problem [48].

In the context of ANN training, the symmetry condition could be applied either as a loss penalty, forcing the equality between the matrix components, or as a hard constraint. For the latter, Jekel et al. [52] proposed a transformation layer, without learnable parameters, to map a vector input to a symmetric positive definite matrix. The transformation is based on the Cholesky factorization of a real symmetric matrix \mathbf{C} , expressed as:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{L}^T, \tag{20}$$

where \mathbf{L} is a real-valued lower triangular matrix, defined as:

$$\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & & & & & \\ L_{21} & L_{22} & & & & \\ L_{31} & L_{32} & L_{33} & & & \\ & & & L_{44} & & \\ & & & & L_{55} & \\ & & & & & L_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \tag{21}$$

with the diagonal elements kept positive, to force the output matrix to be symmetric positive definite. The positiveness of the diagonal elements is enforced with a suitable activation function (e.g. ReLU). Xu et al. [48], on the other hand, propose obtaining \mathbf{L} directly through the ANN output.

2.2.4. Time-consistency

A consistent material law maps a state of zero strain onto a state of zero stress, such that [28,48]:

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \sigma = 0. \quad (22)$$

2.2.5. Stress triaxiality and lode angle parameter

The stress triaxiality and the Lode angle parameter are two dimensionless quantities that can characterize a mechanical state. The stress triaxiality represents the distribution of stress in the three orthotropic axes and is defined as:

$$\mathcal{T} = \frac{\sigma_h}{\sigma_{vM}} \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_h = \text{tr}(\sigma), \quad (23)$$

where σ_h the hydrostatic stress and σ_{vM} the von Mises equivalent stress. Triaxiality range is $-\infty \leq \mathcal{T} \leq +\infty$, however, for a two-dimensional plane stress state, the range reduces to $-2/3 \leq \mathcal{T} \leq 2/3$. A negative value of triaxiality, indicates a compressive stress state, while a positive value corresponds to a tensile state.

The Lode angle θ , or the Lode parameter L , relates the third invariant J_3 of the deviatoric stress tensor σ' with the von Mises equivalent stress σ_{vM} [53], such that:

$$L = -\cos(3\theta) = -\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}^3}\right)^3 \quad \text{with} \quad J_3 = \det(\sigma'). \quad (24)$$

The Lode angle range is $0 \leq \theta \leq \pi/3$ and the Lode parameter range is $-1 \leq L \leq 1$. The Lode angle θ can be normalized as follows:

$$\bar{\theta} = 1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \arccos\left(\frac{J_3}{\sigma_{vM}^3}\right). \quad (25)$$

For a plane stress state, the Lode angle θ and the stress triaxiality \mathcal{T} are related through the following:

$$\theta = \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(1 - \bar{\theta})\right) = -\frac{27}{2}\mathcal{T}\left(\mathcal{T}^2 - \frac{1}{3}\right). \quad (26)$$

2.2.6. Requirements implemented as constraints

Table 1 lists all the previously described requirements and the corresponding formulation to encode them as constraints in the training stage of the data-driven material model. The simplest form of implementation is to add the constraints to the loss function as penalty terms, which are listed in the second column of Table 1. Worthy of note is the fact that these constraints must be adapted for more complex regimes, such as the dynamic regime.

Table 1
Formulation of the loss penalty terms for different constitutive requirements.

Condition	Loss penalty
Clausius-Duhem	$\mathcal{L}_{CD} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU}\left(-\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_{(k)} - \sigma_{(k)}^*) : \Delta\epsilon_{(k)}\right)^2$
Plastic power	$\mathcal{L}_{wP} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU}\left(-\sigma_{(k)} : \dot{\epsilon}_{(k)}^p\right)^2$
Drucker's postulate	$\mathcal{L}_{Drucker} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU}\left(\Delta\sigma_{(k)} : \Delta\epsilon_{(k)}\right)^2$
Tangent symmetry	$\mathcal{L}_{TS} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{j=1}^2 (C_{ij(k)} - C_{ji(k)})^2$
Time-consistency	$\mathcal{L}_{Cons} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} (\sigma(\epsilon = \mathbf{0})_{i(k)})^2$
Stress triaxiality	$\mathcal{L}_{Triax} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU}\left(- \mathcal{T}_{(k)} + \frac{2}{3}\right)^2$
Lode angle	$\mathcal{L}_{\theta} = \frac{\lambda}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N \text{ReLU}\left(- \theta_{(k)}^- + 1\right)^2$

3. GRU-based RNNs

3.1. Introduction

The history-dependent behaviour in plasticity is challenging to model with ANNs [18]. Feedforward architectures are unable to capture the phenomena, as there is no mechanism to relate the inputs in the current time step with the outputs from previous time steps [13,14]. This interdependency between past and present states makes material behaviour data time-dependent, effectively transforming the modelling task into a time-series problem. This scenario constitutes an ideal use-case for RNNs, which allow to maintain a memory of previous inputs using cyclic connections (see Fig. 2(b)) [54]. Using strain sequences with a history of k length, up to the current time step t , a RNN can capture temporal dependencies, allowing it to predict the corresponding stress state accurately.

3.2. Mathematical formulation

In this paper a RNN architecture based on Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) is employed. GRUs are a streamlined version of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) units, designed to capture dependencies in sequential data efficiently, while mitigating some computational complexity [55]. As observed in Fig. 2(a), a basic GRU cell comprises the following key components [55,56]:

1. **Update gate** (z_t) - determines how much is retained from the previous hidden state and how much it should be updated with new information, defined as:

$$z_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xz}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xz} + \mathbf{W}_{hz}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hz}); \quad (27)$$

2. **Reset gate** (r_t) - specifies which information from the previous hidden state should be forgotten, i.e.:

$$r_t = \text{sig}(\mathbf{W}_{xr}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xr} + \mathbf{W}_{hr}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hr}); \quad (28)$$

3. **New gate** (n_t) - computes a new candidate hidden state based on the input and previous hidden state, written as:

$$\mathbf{n}_t = \tanh(\mathbf{W}_{xn}\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{b}_{xn} + r_t \odot [\mathbf{W}_{hn}\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_{hn}]); \quad (29)$$

4. **Final state** (\mathbf{h}_t) - combines the previous hidden state and the new memory content, controlled by the update gate, through the following relationship:

$$\mathbf{h}_t = (1 - z_t) \odot \mathbf{n}_t + z_t \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1}. \quad (30)$$

The variables \mathbf{h}_t and \mathbf{x}_t are, respectively, the hidden state and the input at time t , while $\mathbf{h}_{(t-1)}$ is the hidden state at time $t-1$, or the initial hidden state at $t=0$. The entities sig and tanh are, respectively, the sigmoid and the hyperbolic tangent activation functions and the operator \odot is the Hadamard product. The weight matrices \mathbf{W} and bias vectors \mathbf{b} are appended with double indices identifying the mapping between the different components of the GRU cell. A deeper description of these mathematical entities and their corresponding dimensions, in the context of the present work, is provided in Table 2. The hidden state \mathbf{h} is the key element behind the flow of information relating previous time steps and future predictions. In a way analogous to the internal variables of classical constitutive laws, \mathbf{h} carries the information about the current plastic state of the material [19].

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of (a) a standard GRU cell and (b) an unrolled recurrent neural network.

Table 2

Mathematical entities, and corresponding dimensions for a GRU-based RNN where n is the batch size, k the sequence length, n_{cells} the number of GRU cells, s_{in} the input size, s_{out} the output size and s_{hid} the hidden size.

Component	Entity	Dimensions	Description
Input	\mathbf{x}_t	$(n \times k \times s_{\text{in}})$	Strain sequences
Previous state	\mathbf{h}_{t-1}	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time $t-1$
Final state	\mathbf{h}_t	$(n_{\text{cells}} \times n \times k \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden state at time t
Output	$\hat{\mathbf{y}}_t$	$(n \times s_{\text{out}})$	Stress tensor at time t
Update gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{in}})$	Input to hidden weights of 1st GRU cell
Reset gate or New gate	$\mathbf{W}_{x(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden weights of i th GRU cell
	$\mathbf{b}_{x(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Input to hidden bias
	$\mathbf{W}_{h(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}} \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden weights
	$\mathbf{b}_{h(z r)n}$	$(3 \times s_{\text{hid}})$	Hidden to hidden bias

4. Materials and methods

4.1. RNN architecture

Two RNN architectures were considered, with the following base components: two GRU cells followed by a fully-connected layer with 32 hidden units. One configuration predicts the stress tensor in vector form, while the other outputs the material tangent

stiffness \mathbf{H} , given the addition of an SPD layer as proposed by Jekel et al. [52] (see Section 2.2.3), adapted here to the context of an isotropic material under plane stress. Both RNNs process strain sequences of length $k = 4$. A schematic representation of both architectures is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. GRU-based RNN architectures for material modelling. Sequences of length $k = 4$ of the scaled strain tensor $\epsilon' = [\epsilon'_{xx} \ \epsilon'_{yy} \ \epsilon'_{xy}]$ are taken as input and (a) mapped to the stress tensor $\sigma = [\sigma_{xx} \ \sigma_{yy} \ \tau_{xy}]$ or (b) to the material tangent stiffness \mathbf{H} through the inclusion of an SPD layer. The block identified as FC represents a linear fully-connected layer.

4.2. Training database

Synthetic data to train the RNN models was gathered from a set of FEA simulations of a heterogeneous biaxial test based on a cruciform specimen with a thickness $h = 1$ mm and dimensions specified in Fig. 4(a) [57]. Symmetry boundary conditions were defined at the edges $y = 0$ and $x = 0$, with displacements being prescribed at each arm of the specimen, as depicted in Fig. 4(b). Several virtual experiments were generated with displacements of different magnitudes (in mm), being prescribed in pairs (u_x, u_y) as detailed in Table 3.

Table 3
Paired combinations of displacements (u_x, u_y) prescribed to the arms of the cruciform specimen.

		u_y					
		0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
u_x	0.5	(0.5,0.5)	(0.5,1.0)	(0.5,1.5)	(0.5,2.0)	(0.5,2.5)	(0.5,3.0)
	1.0	(1.0,0.5)	(1.0,1.0)	(1.0,1.5)	(1.0,2.0)	(1.0,2.5)	(1.0,3.0)
	1.5	(1.5,0.5)	(1.5,1.0)	(1.5,1.5)	(1.5,2.0)	(1.5,2.5)	(1.5,3.0)
	2.0	(2.0,0.5)	(2.0,1.0)	(2.0,1.5)	(2.0,2.0)	(2.0,2.5)	(2.0,3.0)
	2.5	(2.5,0.5)	(2.5,1.0)	(2.5,1.5)	(2.5,2.0)	(2.5,2.5)	(2.5,3.0)
	3.0	(3.0,0.5)	(3.0,1.0)	(3.0,1.5)	(3.0,2.0)	(3.0,2.5)	(3.0,3.0)

The simulations were carried out with Abaqus Standard software, assuming plane stress conditions and a small strain formulation. The material behaviour was considered isotropic, with the flow stress evolving according to the Swift's law:

$$\sigma_y = K (\epsilon_0 + \bar{\epsilon}^p)^n \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon_0 = \left(\frac{\sigma_0}{K}\right)^{1/n}, \quad (31)$$

where σ_y is the flow stress, $\bar{\epsilon}^p$ the equivalent plastic strain, σ_0 the initial yield stress, K and n are material-specific hardening parameters. The complete set of constitutive parameters is listed in Table 4.

The geometry was discretized using CPS4R elements with an average size of 0.52 mm, resulting in a total of 2121 elements. Similar refinement levels are cited in the literature for this type of specimen ([57,58], among others). Reduced integration elements were chosen in order to simulate DIC subsets from full-field measurements, thus, field output variables were extracted at the centroid of the element. For each time stage, the strain and stress tensors were extracted at all the measurement points and the resultant force applied at each of the specimen's arms was computed from the equilibrium of the internal forces, through the following:

$$Fl = \sum_{i=1}^n \sigma_i A_i h, \quad (32)$$

where F is the global force, l the length of the specimen, n is the number of elements, A is the area of the element and h the thickness.

Table 4
Constitutive parameters for the soft steel material.

E [GPa]	ν	σ_0 [MPa]	K [MPa]	n
210	0.33	160	565	0.26

The generated dataset consisted of a total of 36 virtual experiments. These were posteriorly shuffled and split in half, such that one part was used for training and the remaining part for validation. The training set was then split such that 80% of the included virtual experiments were used for training and the remaining 20% for testing. The full training domain is shown on the scatter plot from Fig. 5. In terms of major and minor strains, most of the points are under uniaxial tension with a small portion experiencing a slight shear, induced by the prescribed displacements of different magnitudes, resulting in a maximum equivalent plastic strain of 0.329. Concerning the yield locus, most of the stress points evolve towards the first quadrant.

The input data was scaled to have zero mean and unit variance, as follows:

$$\epsilon' = \frac{\epsilon - \mu}{s}, \quad (33)$$

where ϵ' is the scaled strain tensor, $\mu = [\mu_{\epsilon_{xx}} \ \mu_{\epsilon_{yy}} \ \mu_{\epsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of mean values and $s = [s_{\epsilon_{xx}} \ s_{\epsilon_{yy}} \ s_{\epsilon_{xy}}]$ is the vector of variances of the strain tensor components, respectively. The statistical variables μ and s were saved for later usage. For each virtual experiment, the inputs have dimensions $[n_{\text{pts}} \times n_t \times k \times 3]$, where n_{pts} is the number of measurement points, i.e. the number of elements, n_t is the number of time stages, k the RNN sequence length and the last dimension is the number of strain components.

Fig. 4. Biaxial test virtual experiment setup: (a) general dimensions of the cruciform specimen and (b) set of applied boundary conditions.

4.2.1. Training procedure

For the purpose of this work, four GRU-based RNN models were trained and given the nomenclature specified in Table 5, based on the applied constraints. The models were trained using PyTorch library, following a standard supervised learning approach with labelled data. Training was carried out using the Adam optimizer with a weight decay factor of 10^{-3} . A linear warmup scheduler was employed in order to increase the learning rate from an initial value of 10^{-3} up to 5×10^{-3} within the first five epochs. From

Fig. 5. Principal strain and yield locus diagrams for the complete set of virtual experiments used for training, taken from the material points at all the time stages. The yield locus is normalized by the yield stress σ_Y . The greyed-out points correspond to elastic stress states.

that point onward, a gradual decay was applied according to a cosine annealing scheduler defined as [59,60]:

$$\eta_t = \eta_{\min} + \frac{1}{2} (\eta_{\max} - \eta_{\min}) \left(1 + \cos \left(\frac{T_{\text{cur}}}{T_{\text{max}}} \pi \right) \right), \quad (34)$$

where η_t is the current learning rate, η_{\min} and η_{\max} are the minimum and maximum learning rates, T_{cur} and T_{max} are the current iteration and the maximum number of iterations, respectively. The maximum learning rate η_{\max} was set to 5×10^{-3} and the minimum learning rate η_{\min} to 10^{-3} . At the start of each epoch the feeding order of the virtual experiments was shuffled. The corresponding input data was also shuffled along the first dimension and fed to the network as mini-batches due to GPU memory limitations. An early-stopping criterion was defined in order to prevent overfitting, such that training would be interrupted if no further improvement was registered in the test loss after 300 epochs. The data loss was based on the mean squared error between the RNN predicted stress, $\hat{\sigma} = \mathcal{M}(\theta, \epsilon)$ and the target stress σ , defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\theta, \epsilon) = \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{\sigma}(\theta, \epsilon) - \sigma)^2, \quad (35)$$

where n is the number of training samples. The physics-based constraints were enforced by adding penalty terms to the data loss, resulting in a total loss equivalent to a multi-objective loss with the general form:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta, \epsilon) = \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i \mathcal{L}_i, \quad (36)$$

where the constants λ_i are the pre-factors used to balanced the different terms in the loss function, \mathcal{L}_i is the i th objective loss to minimize and k is the total number of conflicting objectives. The pre-factors λ_i can be found through trial and error or through laborious grid-search methods, which may become intractable depending on problem's dimension. As such, an automated scheme to dynamically choose the pre-factors λ_i is preferable. For the purpose, the Relative Loss Balancing with Random Lookback algorithm, introduced by Bischof and Kraus (2021) [61], is employed in the present work. The algorithm dynamically adapts the pre-factors λ_i based on a moving average and a random lookback mechanism. At each iteration the pre-factors are computed as follows:

$$\lambda_i^j = \alpha \left(\beta \lambda_i^{j-1} + (1 - \beta) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j,j^0} \right) + (1 - \alpha) \hat{\lambda}_i^{j,j-1}, \quad (37)$$

where λ_i^j is the prefactor for the i th loss term at iteration j , α is the moving average parameter and β a Bernoulli random variable with a value close to 1. A term $\hat{\lambda}_i^{j,j^0}$ is responsible for computing the scalings based on the relative improvements of each loss between iterations j and j^0 , such that:

$$\hat{\lambda}_i^{j,j^0} = k \cdot \frac{\exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_i^{j^0} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_i^j}{\mathcal{L}_i^{j^0}} \right) \right)}{\sum_{m=1}^k \exp \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\tau \mathcal{L}_m^{j^0} + \epsilon} - \max \left(\frac{\mathcal{L}_m^j}{\mathcal{L}_m^{j^0}} \right) \right)}, \quad (38)$$

with k being the total number of loss terms, \mathcal{L}_i^j and $\mathcal{L}_i^{j^0}$ the values of the i th loss term at iterations j and j^0 , respectively, τ is a hyperparameter that controls the amplitude of the scalings and ϵ a small number. The parameter α controls the weight given to past scalings in relation to the scalings from the current iteration, while β allows the model to occasionally look back until the start of training. For the present work, a simple grid search study confirmed the optimal values for these parameters were: $\alpha = 0.999$, $\beta = 1.0$ and $\tau = 0.001$.

5. The importance of validation

In data-driven constitutive modelling, there is no standardized validation procedure to evaluate the performance of the trained models. Conventionally, model validation in ML is ensured by partitioning the dataset into training and validation sets (unseen

Table 5
Constraints used for each model and corresponding identifiers.

Model	Constraints
Baseline	None
SPD-RNN	SPD layer
Wp-RNN	Plastic power penalty
SPDw-RNN	SPD layer and plastic power penalty

data). The predictive quality of the model is then evaluated based on the latter, according to different statistical metrics (e.g. mean squared error, root mean squared error, among others). Nonetheless, in addition to these metrics, objective indicators should be used to assess whether the resulting data-driven model is able to reproduce the behaviour of material under analysis and to what degree its results should be trusted. This may be achieved by conducting tests based on experiments that generate loading paths that were not included in the original dataset. Regarding the numerical behaviour and its robustness, it is essential to assess how the data-driven constitutive model integrates with a numerical solver. This includes evaluating the possibility of obtaining a consistent tangent matrix and the overall convergence and numerical stability of the model. To address these challenges, this paper explores four different validation approaches to evaluate the quality of the developed RNN-based constitutive models. First, the base performance is evaluated using statistical metrics to predict material responses on previously unseen datasets, under various loading conditions. Second, the model's robustness is assessed using tests based on heterogeneous mechanical specimens, different from the one used for training. Additionally, a set of potential key performance indicators (KPI) that can be used to further validate the performance of data-driven constitutive model are shown. Finally, various single-element tests are conducted and evaluated after integrating the developed model into a user material subroutine (UMAT) of the FEM numerical solver.

5.1. Validation database and procedure

From the data generation phase, 18 virtual experiments based on the cruciform specimen were kept separate for the validation set. This set of experiments had different prescribed displacements than the ones used for training. From the validation set, the virtual experiment with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm was chosen for further analysis. Three additional heterogeneous mechanical specimens, documented in the literature for constitutive model calibration, have also been considered for validation purposes, each of which exhibiting increasing levels of geometric complexity within the respective regions of interest (ROI): the S specimen [62], the Sigma specimen [63] and the D specimen [64]. For further details on each specimen's configuration, the reader is invited to refer to the corresponding original works. An uniaxial external load along the y -direction is normally applied to each specimen. The complex shapes induce multiaxial heterogeneous stress states, despite the loading being uniaxial. For the purpose of the present work, a displacement u_y is prescribed at the top-surface of each specimen with magnitude 2.0 mm for the D specimen and 1.5 mm for the S and Sigma specimens. The corresponding geometries, principal strain distributions, yield locus and equivalent plastic strain field are described in are detailed in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively.

Fig. 6. Geometric definition of the three heterogeneous mechanical specimens chosen for model validation: (a) S specimen, (b) Sigma specimen and (c) D specimen.

Fig. 7. Major and minor strain distributions, normalized yield locus and equivalent plastic strain at the last time stage for (a) the cruciform specimen with prescribed displacements $u_x = u_y = 1.5$ mm, (b) the S specimen (c) the Sigma specimen and (d) the D specimen. The grey colour highlights material points in the elastic regime.

5.2. Error statistics

For the validation dataset, based on the cruciform specimen, model performance was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE), a standard benchmark metric in ML to assess the accuracy of predictive models. A lower RMSE indicates higher accuracy. RMSE quantifies the average magnitude of errors between the predicted and observed values as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{\sigma} - \sigma)^2}, \quad (39)$$

where, $\hat{\sigma}$ is the predicted stress, σ the actual stress and N the number of observations. Additionally, the absolute error, i.e.:

$$\delta = |\hat{\sigma} - \sigma| \quad (40)$$

was used to compare the predicted stress fields and stress–strain curves with the reference FEA solution.

5.3. Validation KPI: reconstructed axial force ratio

The reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR), introduced by Peshave et al. [65] was also employed to evaluate the performance of the RNN-based constitutive models. The RAFR exploits the fact that in uniaxial tensile tests, the load applied by the testing machine F_a is known. Moreover, the horizontal average of the stress multiplied by the cross-sectional area F_c^i should be equal to the applied load at any cross-section (see Fig. 8). For a given cross-section i , the reconstructed force F_c^i is computed by integrating the axial stress σ_{yy} , as follows:

$$F_c^i = \int_{S_c} \sigma_{yy} dS_c, \quad (41)$$

where S_c is the surface of that particular cross-section of the mechanical specimen. Assuming constant stress through the thickness, the surface integral reduces to:

$$F_c^i = h \int_{l_i} \sigma_{yy} dl_i, \quad (42)$$

where h is the specimen's thickness. Considering a regular grid of measurement points with sufficiently high spatial density, the line integral can be approximated as:

$$F_c^i = h S_t \sum_{j=1}^{N_i} \sigma_{yy}^j, \quad (43)$$

where N_i is the number of evaluation points at the cross-section i and S_t is the step size. The RAFR is then computed as:

$$RAFR = \frac{F_c^i}{F_a}. \quad (44)$$

The metric is used to evaluate how well the section-averaged stress field matches the applied force at each cross-section. Any deviation from the ideal value of 1 indicates inconsistencies with the approximation of the actual stress field.

Fig. 8. Schematic of RAFR calculation. The force acting at the i th cross-section is reconstructed by integrating the corresponding axial stress σ_{yy}^i along the cross-section length l_i and multiplying it by the thickness h .

5.4. UMAT implementation

Another step taken to validate the trained RNN models, involved incorporating them as material constitutive models in a FEA solver (here, Abaqus Standard), through a custom user material subroutine (UMAT). The code was developed in C++ and made use of the official C++ implementation of PyTorch (LibTorch). The architecture and data flow for the UMAT implementation are described in the flowchart of Fig. 9.

The Python-based RNN models were converted to an appropriate format in order to work in the Python-independent environment. All the RNN operations were implemented as a function in a dynamic-link library (DLL) (annlib.dll). The UMAT is the interface between Abaqus Standard and the DLL, dealing with the inputs/outputs and updating the strain history. The DLL function is invoked in the UMAT code and receives the strain history, the mean and the variance of the training data as input arguments. Within the DLL function, the strain history is scaled to have zero mean and unit variance. The RNN model is loaded persistently into memory in the code's first execution. The scaled strain history is fed as input to the RNN in order to predict the stress tensor, which is returned as an output back to the UMAT, along with the stiffness matrix. The UMAT implementation was used to validate the RNN-based material models performance on one-element tests, specifically uniaxial traction along x - and y -directions and a shear test. Within this validation step, numerical issues, such as stability, convergence and efficiency can also be evaluated.

Fig. 9. Flowchart of the UMAT-RNN implementation.

6. Results

6.1. Learning curves and the effect of constraints

Regarding the baseline model (Fig. 10(a)), both train and test losses sharply decrease during the initial 50 to 100 epochs, followed by a gradual evolution for the remaining epochs of training. The oscillations exhibited by the loss curves reveal a certain difficulty in achieving convergence. Nonetheless, the early-stopping triggered at epoch 1383, saving the model state at this point with a train and test loss of 1.3182 MPa² and 2.2190 MPa², respectively. The learning curves for the SPD-RNN model (Fig. 10(b)) exhibit a similar learning pattern, however with notably fewer oscillations, suggesting improved stability and training convergence. The early-stopping was triggered at epoch 848, corresponding to a train loss of 0.951 MPa² and a test loss of 1.723 MPa². The Wp-RNN model also exhibits similar behaviour (Fig. 10(c)) with the loss curves showing slightly less noise when compared to the baseline model. The early-stopping was triggered after 901 epochs, corresponding to a train and test loss of 1.588 MPa² and 2.249 MPa², respectively. The SPDw-RNN learning curves (Fig. 10(d)) follow the general learning pattern, albeit with considerably less noise. Additionally, the model was faster to train, with the early-stopping being triggered after 444 epochs, corresponding to a train and test loss of 1.015 MPa² and 1.777 MPa², respectively. For all the models, the gap between the train and test losses is not significant, indicating the RNNs did not overfit.

For the Wp-RNN model, the plastic power penalty term (Fig. 11(a)) sharply increases at the beginning of training, from 10⁻⁴ J s⁻¹ to 10⁻² J s⁻¹, approximately, followed by a rapid decrease which is tied to the overall learning pattern of the Wp-RNN model. At the early-stopping point, a lower value of 2.85 × 10⁻⁵ J s⁻¹ was registered. The sharp increase at the beginning of training is due to the fact that the stresses predicted by the RNN are initially small in magnitude, resulting in a low value of plastic power. As the training evolves, the predicted stresses get progressively higher in magnitude, causing the plastic power to increase up to a certain point, from which it starts to decrease due to further improvements in the prediction quality. The loss pre-factors were continuously adjusted during training in order to balance both terms of the loss function, oscillating within a narrow range from 0.96 to 1.06. In contrast, for the SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 11(b)) the plastic power penalty appears smooth and sharply increases from a residual value of approximately 10⁻¹³ J s⁻¹ at the beginning of training to quickly saturate at around the final value of 1.79 × 10⁻⁵ J s⁻¹ at the early-stopping point. The loss balancing terms follow a similar pattern to the Wp-RNN model, oscillating within the same range.

Fig. 10. Learning curves for the trained RNN-based material models. Effect of the physics-based constraints on the training and test losses.

(a) Wp-RNN

(b) SPDw-RNN

Fig. 11. Plastic power penalty loss \mathcal{L}_{W_p} and loss balancing pre-factors for (a) the Wp-RNN and (b) the SPDw-RNN models during training.

6.2. Model validation with different mechanical specimens

6.2.1. Mechanical test with cruciform specimen

The von Mises stress contours for the cruciform specimen obtained with the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 12 and the corresponding RMSE statistics on the validation set are presented in Table 6. The stress distribution for this particular specimen ranges from 71.483 to 357.858 MPa, with high stress concentrations located at the inner regions of the central hole. Results show the stress field predicted by the baseline RNN model (Fig. 12(a)) closely follows the reference, albeit small discrepancies are visible near the smaller radii. The absolute error ranges from 0.002 to 5.817 MPa, with a mean error of 0.433 MPa. The SPD-RNN model (Fig. 12(b)) demonstrates higher predictive accuracy compared to the baseline model, as it closely matches the reference results. The overall error for this model ranges from 0.006 to 2.131 MPa, with a mean error of 0.289 MPa. There is a significant reduction in the maximum error compared to the baseline model, the lower mean error further highlights its superior predictive capability and generalization. Concerning the Wp-RNN model (Fig. 12(c)), predictions have only slightly improved upon the baseline. The absolute error for the Wp-RNN ranges from 0.011 to 3.587 MPa, with a mean error of 0.415 MPa. The SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 12(d)) results are on par with the SPD-RNN, albeit with slightly worse mean and median errors. The absolute error ranges from 0.016 to 2.437 MPa.

Table 6
RMSE statistics for the validation set based on the cruciform specimen.

Model	RMSE validation set			
	Min.	Mean	Median	Max.
Baseline	0.7228	1.4464	1.2441	2.8477
SPD-RNN	0.6593	1.2801	1.0834	2.6489
Wp-RNN	0.6923	1.4341	1.2285	2.8264
SPDw-RNN	0.6903	1.3080	1.0959	2.6522

6.2.2. Mechanical test with s specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the S specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 13. The stress distribution ranges from 8.233 to 336.823 MPa, with the higher stress concentrations occurring at the narrower areas near the notches' roots. The Baseline model results (Fig. 13(a)) show the predicted stress field closely matches the reference results, although some discrepancies are registered mainly along the linear areas of the notches. The absolute error varies between 0.017 and 77.833 MPa, with a mean error of 1.885 MPa. Concerning the SPD-RNN model (Fig. 13(b)), results have improved compared to the baseline model, with mean absolute error being reduced to 1.642 MPa and the overall error ranging between 0.003 and 88.672 MPa. The Wp-RNN model (Fig. 13(c)) also shows an improvement in prediction accuracy compared to the baseline. The maximum absolute error decreases to 50.579 MPa and the minimum absolute error slightly increased to 0.027 MPa, while the mean error is the lowest among the four models, at 1.541 MPa. The error statistics show the Wp-RNN model is particularly effective at minimizing discrepancies, however with the SPD-RNN those are much more localized. The SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 13(d)) results are similar to that of the SPD-RNN, however with higher median and maximum absolute errors. The error ranges from 0.003 to 116.799 MPa.

Fig. 14 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Large discrepancies are observed at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models, except for the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN which achieved a relatively flat curve, suggesting that those models are able to output time-consistent solutions. For larger loads, all the models produce similar results, the curves are smoother near the edges of the specimen with a slight scatter visible at the regions between the notches, where the stress state is more complex. The three models behave well within the $\pm 10\%$ grey area, nonetheless the Wp-RNN model seems to be prone to higher deviations.

6.2.3. Mechanical test with sigma specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the Sigma specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 15. The stress distribution ranges from 0.537 to 238.012 MPa, with higher stress concentrations around the curved features of the specimen, located at the centre and near the top and bottom regions. The baseline RNN model (Fig. 15(a)) approximates the reference results relatively well, however with notable discrepancies over the top half of the specimen. The minimum and maximum absolute error are 0.022 MPa and 101.132 MPa respectively, with a mean absolute error of 3.995 MPa. Regarding the SPD-RNN (Fig. 15(b)), the full-field plots show a significant degradation of the results, with the white blobs showing that the model tends to underestimate the stress on those regions. The statistics show higher maximum and the mean absolute errors, calculated at 452.666 and 5.88 MPa respectively. Nonetheless, the error regions are narrower and the significantly lower median error suggests an overall improvement in prediction accuracy. The Wp-RNN model's (Fig. 15(c)) predictions are slightly better than the baseline and SPD-RNN model. The absolute error ranges from 0.012 to 77.286 MPa, with a mean absolute error of 3.827 MPa. The SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 15(d)) approximates the reference results quite well with no visible degradation, in contrast with the SPD-RNN. Compared to the latter, although the discrepancies are less localized, the overall results have improved achieving significantly lower mean and maximum errors. The absolute error ranges from 0.001 to 175.072 MPa.

Fig. 16 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Similarly to the S specimen, large discrepancies are still present at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models. An exception is made for the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN

models, which achieved a relatively flat curve, once again suggesting that the SPD hard constraint allows the models to achieve time-consistent solutions. For larger loads, the RAFR metric improves for all the models, with the baseline and the Wp-RNN originating similar curves. Significant scatter is evident for these models towards the last time stages, slightly exceeding the $\pm 10\%$ error. Worthy of note is the robustness of the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models, originating relatively flat curves with only a slight scatter near the radial features of the specimen. Nonetheless, punctual but significant deviations going beyond the error zone are registered for the SPD-RNN on the last time stage. For the SPDw-RNN the deviations are always kept inside the $\pm 10\%$ error zone. For all the models, these discrepancies appear to happen at the coordinates of the regions consistent with the error maps from Fig. 15.

Fig. 12. Cruciform specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 124$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 13. S specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 120$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 14. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the S specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value RAFR = 1 is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The vertical dashed lines indicate the location of each notch root. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

6.2.4. Mechanical test with D specimen and RAFR KPI

The von Mises stress contours for the D specimen corresponding to the four RNN models under analysis are shown in Fig. 17. The stress distribution ranges from 0.145 to 326.129 MPa, with stress concentrations located around the inner and corner curved regions as well as on the vertical member of the specimen. The baseline RNN model (Fig. 17(a)) manages to approximate the reference results, however some discrepancies are evident. The minimum and maximum absolute error are 0.00 and 113.485 MPa respectively, with a mean absolute error of 3.1 MPa. Regarding the SPD-RNN (Fig. 17(b)), there is an evident degradation of the results in the top and bottom corners of the inner cutout, with the white blobs showing a slight tendency for the model to underestimate the stress on those areas. The maximum and the mean absolute errors are also higher than the baseline model, calculated at 1528.155 and 4.54 MPa, respectively. However, the median error is of similar magnitude, indicating that there is not a significant degradation on the overall prediction accuracy and the highest errors are present only on those very narrow regions. Regarding the Wp-RNN model (Fig. 17(c)) error statistics seem to indicate that the prediction accuracy has improved upon the baseline and SPD-RNN models. The absolute error ranges from 0.004 to 94.075 MPa, with a mean absolute error of 2.8 MPa. Nonetheless, for the Wp-RNN model the error is spread over a wider region. For the SPDw-RNN model (Fig. 17(d)), degradation was reduced compared to the SPD-RNN, albeit it is still present at the top and bottom corners of the inner cutout. The maximum absolute error has improved, nonetheless the median has slightly increased. The absolute error ranges from 0.0 to 719.054 MPa.

Fig. 18 shows the RAFR metric calculated for the four RNN-based models. Large discrepancies are still present at lower loads for both the baseline and Wp-RNN models, albeit with lower magnitude. The SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models show a mostly flat curve. For larger loads, the metric improves for all the models with the baseline and Wp-RNN models showing a similar behaviour. A significant deviation is evident for these models at the lower-half of the specimen towards the last time stages, nonetheless still within the $\pm 10\%$ error area. Once again, the SPD-RNN and SPDw-RNN models show robustness, originating mostly flat curves with only a slight discrepancy at the lower-half of the specimen, which is consistent with the errors shown in Fig. 17.

The error statistics for the stress fields predicted by each RNN model, for all heterogeneous mechanical specimens, are summarized in Table 7. This table allows for the comparison of various model performances and highlight the impact of incorporating constraints during model training. Notably, among all the models trained using stress-strain fields from cruciform specimen, the models incorporated with constraints, particularly, SPD-RNN and Wp-RNN, demonstrate significantly enhanced performance compared to baseline model.

6.3. One-element tests

The uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves obtained for the one-element tests performed with the UMAT implementations of the four RNN models under analysis and the corresponding absolute error along the time stages are shown in Figs. 19 and 20, respectively. The curves are compared with the FEA solution and with the RNNs' inference predictions.

Fig. 15. Sigma specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 120$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 16. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the Sigma specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value RAFR = 1 is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

Table 7
Error statistics for the stress predicted by each model for each mechanical specimen, and training cost shown in epochs.

Specimens		Model absolute error [MPa]			
		Baseline	SPD-RNN	Wp-RNN	SPDw-RNN
Epochs		1683	1148	1201	744
Min.	Cruciform	0.002	0.006	0.011	0.016
	S	0.017	0.003	0.027	0.003
	Sigma	0.022	0.0	0.012	0.001
	D	0.0	0.0	0.004	0.0
Mean	Cruciform	0.433	0.289	0.415	0.383
	S	1.885	1.602	1.541	1.711
	Sigma	3.995	5.88	3.827	3.59
	D	3.1	4.54	2.8	4.469
Median	Cruciform	0.311	0.204	0.338	0.296
	S	0.882	0.732	0.688	1.015
	Sigma	1.018	0.48	1.148	0.469
	D	0.505	0.543	0.582	0.758
Max.	Cruciform	5.817	2.131	3.587	2.437
	S	77.833	88.672	50.579	116.799
	Sigma	101.132	452.666	77.286	175.072
	D	113.485	1528.155	94.075	719.054
Std. deviation	Cruciform	0.463	0.335	0.381	0.370
	S	5.026	4.227	3.241	5.621
	Sigma	11.169	31.043	9.497	15.181
	D	8.119	41.965	7.126	29.580

Fig. 17. D specimen: contour maps of von Mises equivalent stress at time stage $n_t = 142$ for (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models. Comparison with the FEA solution and corresponding absolute difference.

Fig. 18. Reconstructed axial force ratio (RAFR) for the coordinates along the length (in mm) of the D specimen, for the trained RNN-based models. The ideal value $RAFR = 1$ is denoted by the dashed horizontal line. The greyed-out area represents an error span of $\pm 10\%$.

The results show that, in general, all the models were capable of predicting the uniaxial behaviour very well at both rolling (RD) and transverse (TD) directions with overall low absolute errors. All the models show similar error profiles along the time stages for the x -direction (RD) and the y -direction (TD). However, for the SPD-RNN, the Wp-RNN and the SPDw-RNN models, the error profile shows a small spike reaching a maximum of approximately 6.5 MPa at time stage 24 which onset of yielding. Numerical instabilities were detected with the baseline model for the test along the x -direction (RD), resulting in oscillations towards the final segment of the stress curve.

Regarding the shear response, all the models struggle to approximate the reference curve to some degree, with SPD-RNN and the SPDw-RNN models showing higher levels of degradation, while the baseline and the Wp-RNN models were capable of more stable responses. It is interesting to see that the RNNs were able to capture the material behaviour from the biaxial experiments in such a way that they are still capable of performing relatively well in a completely different setting. The source of the instabilities for the baseline model is essentially of numerical nature, induced by spurious predictions interfering with the equilibrium iterations. As evidenced by the results of the SPD-RNN, Wp-RNN and SPDw-RNN models, the introduction of constraints mitigated those issues. The degradation seen on the shear response curves suggests the training data based on the cruciform specimen is not rich enough in shear states, and it would benefit from the addition of information from that regions of the strain space.

7. Concluding remarks

The importance of validation KPI and physics-based constraints for data-driven constitutive modelling was acknowledged. Within the framework of elastoplasticity, a variety of constitutive requirements were identified, as well as the corresponding theoretical development and possible implementation formulas to use as loss penalty terms in the training process. The importance of the validation stage within the data-driven constitutive modelling workflow was highlighted due to the strict physical requirements. Within this context, it was addressed that the standard error metrics are not sufficient to discern between models and the corresponding predictive accuracy. Therefore, an improved validation routine is proposed, which includes (i) the usual statistical metrics, (ii) tests on unseen data from virtual experiments based on different heterogeneous mechanical specimens, (iii) external KPIs, such as the reconstructed axial force ratio and (iv) single-element FEA tests.

In order to test the effects of different physics-based constraints, and bring into practice the improved validation methodology, four RNN-based models were trained with labelled data to predict the stress tensor based on strain sequences. In general, the results have shown that the addition of constraints improved the models' predictive capacity and extrapolation power as well as faster training times. Moreover, the constrained models also showed improved numerical accuracy and stability when incorporated into a numerical solver. In this context, the SPD-RNN architecture offers an advantage as the model outputs the tangent stiffness matrix directly, bypassing the need to derive it. The formulation acts as a hard constraint and resulted in more accurate and time-consistent solutions when compared to the baseline and the Wp-RNN model with the plastic power constraint. Some constraints were not tested due to time restrictions, however, the corresponding formulation as a penalty terms is still provided in the paper.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 19. Uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves. Comparison between the FEA solution based on the Swift's law (Eq. (31)) and the UMAT implementations of (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 20. Absolute error along the time stages corresponding to the uniaxial tensile and shear strain-stress curves, for the UMAT implementations of (a) the baseline, (b) the SPD-RNN, (c) the Wp-RNN and (d) the SPDw-RNN models.

The proposed validation methodology not only allowed to effectively evaluate the trained models' performance in a wide range of cases beyond the training domain, but also to deeply analyse the physical consistency of the trained models, especially through the RAFR KPI and the numerical one-element tests.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rúben Lourenço: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Aiman Tariq:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petia Georgieva:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition. **A. Andrade-Campos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Babür Deliktaş:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

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Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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